

THE LASER 4 SURF ALL-IN-ONE MACHINE

LASER4SURF's all-in-one machine will overcome the main limitations of laser texturing for mass production. The solution is to merge all independent process steps into one single step: definition of process parameters + functionalisation + in-line inspection.

A new **software platform** will enable industrial end users to select the process parameters for a desired functionality, without the need to fully understand the LIPSS (Laser Induced Periodic Surface Structures) generation process.

A newly developed **optical module** will control the optical power, beam profile, polarisation orientation and the operational wavelength of the micromachining system.

An **in-line monitoring** will verify the different nano properties of the surfaces treated. This single-step process in one machine will lead to a significant reduction of the processing time.

Website
www.laser4surf.eu

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